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Lack of Effectiveness of Computer Aided Detection for Colorectal Neoplasia. A Meta-analysis of Non-Randomized Studies.

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Abstract:	Background Benefits of computer-aided detection (CADE) in detecting colorectal neoplasia were shown in many randomized trials in which endoscopists' behavior was strictly controlled. However, the effect of CADE on endoscopists' performance in less-controlled setting is unclear. This systematic review and meta-analyses were aimed at clarifying benefits and harms of using CADE in real-world colonoscopy.

	<p>Methods We searched MEDLINE, EMBASE, and Google Scholar from inception to August 20, 2023. We included non-randomized studies that compared the effectiveness between CADe-assisted and standard colonoscopy. Two investigators independently extracted study data and quality. Pairwise meta-analysis was performed utilizing Risk ratio (RR) for dichotomous variables and mean difference (MD) for continuous variables with a 95% confidence interval (95% CI).</p> <p>Results Eight studies were included, comprising 9,782 patients (4569 with CADe and 5213 without CADe). Regarding benefits, there was neither a difference in adenoma detection rate (44% vs 38%; RR 1.11 [95% CI 0.97 – 1.28]) nor mean adenoma per colonoscopy (0.93 vs 0.79; MD 0.14 [-0.04 – 0.32]) between the CADe-assisted and standard colonoscopy, respectively. Regarding harms, there was no difference in the mean non-neoplastic lesions per colonoscopy (8 studies included for analysis, 0.52 vs 0.47; MD 0.14 [95% CI -0.07 – 0.34]) and withdrawal time (6 studies included for analysis, 14.3 vs 13.4 minutes; MD 0.8 minutes [95% CI -0.18 – 1.90]). There was a substantial heterogeneity, and all outcomes were graded with a very low certainty of evidence.</p> <p>Conclusion CADe in colonoscopies neither improves the detection of colorectal neoplasia nor increases burden of colonoscopy in real-world, non-randomized studies, questioning the generalizability of the results of randomized trials.</p>
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What You Need to Know

Background: Computer-aided detection (CADe) has been shown to improve adenoma detection rate in randomized, controlled studies. However, evidence for effectiveness in less controlled, real-world setting is conflicting.

Findings: CADe in colonoscopies neither improves the detection of colorectal neoplasia nor increases the burden of colonoscopy in the real-world, non-randomized studies, questioning the generalizability of the results of randomized trials. The simultaneous lack of both is interesting, suggesting possibly either under-utilization or lack of effect of CADe.

Implications for patient care: The contrasting nature of these findings compared to randomized studies implicates a greater role for real world data and raises a question why benefits and harms of CADe are not apparent in clinical practice, perhaps due to a lack of a targeted study design. To address the uncertainties in the current literature, we recommend conducting additional randomized studies in a more pragmatic setting.

Lack of Effectiveness of Computer Aided Detection for Colorectal Neoplasia

A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis of Non-Randomized Studies

CAde Benefits

No difference in ADR	8 studies	RR 1.11 [95%CI 0.97 – 1.28]
-No difference in ADR (Retrospective studies)	4 studies	RR 0.97 [95%CI 0.86 – 1.09]
-increase in ADR (Prospective studies)	4 studies	RR 1.29 [95%CI 1.11 – 1.49]
No difference in AADR	3 studies	RR 0.84 [95%CI 0.59 – 1.20]
No difference in APC	8 studies	MD 0.14 [95%CI -0.04 – 0.32]

CAde Harms

No difference in inspection time	6 studies	MD 0.86 minutes [95% CI -0.18 – 1.90]
No difference in NNLPC	8 studies	MD 0.14 [95% CI -0.07 – 0.34]

ADR = adenoma detection rate; AADR = advanced adenoma detection rate; APC = Mean adenoma per colonoscopy; NNLPC = non-neoplastic lesion per colonoscopy

[Click here to view linked References](#)

Lack of Effectiveness of Computer Aided Detection for Colorectal Neoplasia: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis of Non-Randomized Studies

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Background: Benefits of computer-aided detection (CADE) in detecting colorectal neoplasia were shown in many randomized trials where endoscopists' behavior was strictly controlled. However, the effect of CADe on endoscopists' performance in less-controlled setting is unclear. This systematic review and meta-analyses were aimed at clarifying benefits and harms of using CADe in real-world colonoscopy.

Methods: We searched MEDLINE, EMBASE, Cochrane and Google Scholar from inception to August 20, 2023. We included non-randomized studies that compared the effectiveness between CADe-assisted and standard colonoscopy. Two investigators independently extracted study data and quality. Pairwise meta-analysis was performed utilizing Risk ratio (RR) for dichotomous variables and mean difference (MD) for continuous variables with a 95% confidence interval (95% CI).

Results: Eight studies were included, comprising 9,782 patients (4569 with CADe and 5213 without CADe). Regarding benefits, there was neither a difference in adenoma detection rate (44% vs 38%; RR 1.11 [95% CI 0.97 – 1.28]) nor mean adenoma per colonoscopy (0.93 vs 0.79; MD 0.14 [-0.04 – 0.32]) between the CADe-assisted and standard colonoscopy, respectively. Regarding harms, there was no difference in the mean non-neoplastic lesions per colonoscopy (8 studies included for analysis, 0.52 vs 0.47; MD 0.14 [95% CI -0.07 – 0.34]) and withdrawal time (6 studies included for analysis, 14.3 vs 13.4 minutes; MD 0.8 minutes [95% CI -0.18 – 1.90]). There was a substantial heterogeneity, and all outcomes were graded with a very low certainty of evidence.

Conclusion: CADe in colonoscopies neither improves the detection of colorectal neoplasia nor increases burden of colonoscopy in real-world, non-randomized studies, questioning the generalizability of the results of randomized trials.

Keyword: Colonoscopy, CADe, Artificial Intelligence, ADR, Adenoma

Introduction

Computer-aided detection (CADe) assisted colonoscopy is attracting attention because it is expected to improve the quality of colonoscopy by increasing the adenoma detection rate (ADR)¹, which may lead to reduction of colorectal cancer². The knowledge base of this increased ADR was a meta-analysis that assessed more than twenty randomized controlled trials (RCTs); thus, it could be trustworthy and convincing¹. However, results of RCTs are not necessarily reproducible in clinical practice for two main issues, namely internal and external validity³.

The internal validity of RCTs is assessed by the overall risk of bias of the included RCTs that also affects the level of certainty of the benefits and harms of an intervention. In RCTs on CADe, a major bias was the inability to blind the endoscopist to the tested intervention. Unlike double-blind RCTs for new drugs, where the rater is unaware of the patient's allocation, the endoscopist in CADe RCTs was always aware of the allocated arm. This could potentially introduce a psychological bias, unintentionally favouring the CADe arm.

Secondly, the external validity of CADe-related trials is also uncertain. In a not-highly controlled setting, several factors can unexpectedly influence the effectiveness of CADe. Some endoscopists may consider CADe-activation as false-positives without giving the necessary attention. Furthermore, CADe could possibly have a detrimental effect on the level of attention, resulting in a paradoxical deskilling of the endoscopists.

Both issues can be overcome by conducting non-randomized observational studies where the effectiveness rather than the efficacy of CADe in real-practice is assessed without an immediate and direct comparison between CADe-assisted and standard colonoscopy. The lack of a highly controlled setting reduces the psychological pressure of the endoscopists to demonstrate a possible benefit of CADe (i.e., the operator bias) and allows endoscopists to use CADe according to their preferences and attitudes which we usually experience in a real-world clinical practice. On the other hand, non-controlled factors may affect the outcome of the study, especially when considering that an equivalent distribution of prevalence of disease is required for a fair assessment of the effectiveness of the intervention.

We conducted this systematic review and meta-analysis to pool the evidence on the benefits and harms of using CADe for the detection of colorectal neoplasia in a non-randomized setting.

Methods

This systematic review and meta-analyses were performed according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses statement⁴ (*Supplementary Table 1*). The current review was not registered with any registry. Template data collection forms, data extracted from included studies, data used for all analyses, analytic code, and any other materials used in the review – except where provided in this manuscript, are not made publicly available.

Data Sources and Searches

We screened for observational studies comparing standard colonoscopy with and without real-time use of CADe that were published as full-length articles in databases such as Medline/PubMed, Embase, Cochrane and Google Scholar (all without language restrictions) from inception to August 20, 2023. Artificial intelligence, CADe, computer-aided detection, computer-assisted detection, colonoscopy, colonic polyps, adenoma, adenoma detection, polyp, and polyp detection were all utilized as search terms. A targeted search strategy yielded 948 items (detailed in Appendix), each of which was validated for eligibility. Additional studies were identified by manually searching through the references cited in reviews, meta-analyses, and original publications. Literature search was performed by two authors (HKP and DR).

Study Selection

Full length manuscript publications were considered if they described a non-randomized (retrospective or prospective) investigation of real-time colonoscopy performed by Endoscopist physician (non-trainee) in human adults with and without CADe for any indication. Here, we define the retrospective studies as those in which CADe was used in real-time during colonoscopy, but the data was analyzed in a retrospective fashion. We did not include any retrospective studies in which already recorded images or videos were assessed by endoscopists (so-called bench-mark studies). To critically evaluate if the included papers satisfied the inclusion criteria, the lead review author (HKP) and three supervisory authors (CS, YM, and PS) conducted a consensus discussion. When in need of clarification, the authors were contacted through email. *Supplementary Table 2 provides a more detailed PICOTS (population, interventions, comparisons, outcomes, timing, and setting).*

Data Extraction, Risk of bias and Quality Assessment

Two authors (HKP and DR) independently summarized and recorded data in a standardized format. The collected information included details such as study design, patient characteristics, descriptions of interventions and controls, and study outcomes. Any conflicts or discrepancies in the data were resolved through consensus. To determine if a statistical analysis of the data would yield valuable and meaningful results, we thoroughly examined potential sources of heterogeneity and assessed the risk of bias using ROBINS-I (Risk of Bias in Non-randomised Studies – of Interventions) tool. An overall graphical depiction of the assessment's findings and the risk-scoring methodology were used to convey the bias assessment results.

Outcomes and Definitions

We analyzed the following outcomes in accordance with their contributions to patient care (i.e., benefits and harms):

Benefits

Primary outcome measure

- Adenoma detection rate (ADR): the proportion of colonoscopies in which at least one adenoma was detected. We selected ADR as the main outcome measure of this study because ADR is the only outcome measure which has proved to be associated with cancer prevention effect.

Secondary outcome measures

- Mean adenoma per colonoscopy (APC): the total number of detected adenomas divided by the total number of colonoscopies.
- Polyp detection rate (PDR)⁵: the proportion of colonoscopies in which at least one polyp was detected.
- Advanced adenoma detection rate (AADR): the proportion of colonoscopies in which at least one advanced adenoma was detected (adenoma \geq 1 cm, the presence of villous architecture, or adenoma with high-grade dysplasia).
- Sessile serrated lesion detection rate (SSLDR): the proportion of colonoscopies in which at least one SSL (serrated adenoma, traditional serrated adenoma) was detected.

- Sessile Serrated Lesion Per Colonoscopy (SSLPC): the total number of detected sessile serrated lesions divided by the total number of colonoscopies.
- Adenoma per positive colonoscopy (APPC): the total number of detected adenomas divided by the total number of colonoscopies where at least one adenoma was detected (positive colonoscopy).
- Polyps per colonoscopy (PPC)⁶: the total number of detected polyps divided by total number of colonoscopies.

Harms

- Inspection time: the time spent inspecting the colonic mucosa as the endoscope is withdrawn during colonoscopy.
- Non-neoplastic (hyperplastic, inflammatory, normal mucosa) lesion per colonoscopy: the total number of detected non-neoplastic lesions that were resected, divided by total number of colonoscopies.

Data Synthesis and Analysis

Descriptive statistics were utilized to summarize study characteristics. For direct comparisons, we carried out pairwise meta-analyses, presenting results as risk ratio (RR) for categorical variables and mean difference (MD) for continuous variables with their 95% confidence intervals (CIs). We used RevMan (v 5.4.1) for analysis of categorical variable⁷ and R (v 4.0.3) for all the pooled proportions and statistical computations of continuous variables⁸. If means for continuous variables were not available (1 study⁹), we calculated them from available medians and ranges/interquartile ranges using ‘estmeansd’ R package (based upon a Quantile estimation as well as Box-Cox method)¹⁰. When mean values were available without standard deviation SD (3 studies¹¹⁻¹³) we used imputation methods from the R package ‘MetaGear’ to derive SD¹⁴ (based upon Bracken’s approach to impute SD using the coefficient of variation from all other complete mean and SD pairs in meta-analysis)¹⁵. Statistical significance was determined with two-sided p-values set at ≤ 0.05 . Pooled proportions from both arms for main outcomes of benefits and harms (ADR, APC,>NNLPC and Inspection time) were obtained using R.

Given the expected high level of between-study variability, we used random-effects models for pooling effect sizes. We assessed statistical heterogeneity through the chi-square test and

quantified inconsistency using the I^2 statistic ($I^2 > 50\%$ as substantial heterogeneity). Subgroup analyses were performed to scrutinize clinical variations and robustness of pooled outcomes for categorical variables such as indication, type of study, region of study, type of CADe system employed for study. Meta regression was performed for baseline endoscopist ADR to assess its influence on effect size.

The Grades of Recommendation, Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) approach was used to rate the certainty of our evidence-based conclusions¹⁶. Risk of bias was assessed using ROBINS-I tool by Cochrane which was visualized using the Robvis tool^{17,18}. Heterogeneity was primarily evaluated through visual inspection of forest plots and exploratory analyses. The extent of heterogeneity was also assessed using the I^2 statistic. Begg rank correlation and Egger regression tests were planned to assess for publication bias) but they do not perform well with fewer than 10 studies contributing to a given estimate, and thus they were omitted.

Results

A total of 670 studies were screened and fourteen pragmatic studies were identified for initial analysis. However, six of those studies were later excluded after a consensus discussion because of either unclear methodology^{19–22} or randomized controlled design^{23,24}. Eight studies were then finalized that were eligible for inclusion as seen in *Supplementary Figure 1*. They involved total 9782 patients - 4569 in the CADe-assisted arm (mean age 61.1 years and 50% females) and 5213 in the standard colonoscopy arm (mean age 61.3 years and 51% females)^{9,11–13,25–28}. *Table 1* shows study characteristics and methodologies of all included studies. Four studies are prospective in design^{11,13,25–27} and four are retrospective^{9,12,13,28}. Four studies were performed in the USA (west)^{9,11,27,28}, one each in Japan²⁵, China²⁶ and New Zealand¹³ and Israel¹²(east). Four studies only included patients who underwent a screening or surveillance colonoscopy^{9,11,27,28}. All studies used current high definition (HD) scopes. Three studies used the GI Genius system^{9,12,28} while EndoBrain-Eye²⁵, Scout¹¹, EndoVigilant²⁷, and EndoAid¹³ were used in the remaining studies. Seven studies were monocentric while one study²⁷ was multicentric. Three studies were performed at non-academic community endoscopy centers^{11,13,27} and five studies were performed at academic centers^{9,12,25,26,28}. Five studies used a historical cohort for the non-CADe arm for comparison^{9,11,12,27,28}. One of those studies provided data for both a concurrent control group and a historical control group⁹.

Benefits

Primary outcome measure (Figure 1)

Eight studies compared ADR between both CADe and non-CADe arms, and we did not find any difference (pooled estimates of 44% vs 38%, RR 1.11 [95% CI 0.97 – 1.28, 95% PI 0.55 – 2.60]; $I^2 = 83\%$, very low certainty evidence (see *Supplementary Table 3*)).

Secondary Outcomes (Supplementary Figures 3-16)

There was no difference between CADe and non-CADe arms for advanced adenoma detection rate (AADR)^{9,12,25} (Three studies, RR 0.84 [95% CI 0.59 – 1.20], $I^2 = 65\%$) or SSLDR^{9,11-13,25,27,28} (Seven studies, RR 1.01 [95% CI 0.84 – 1.20]; $I^2 = 0\%$, very low certainty evidence (see *Supplementary Table 3*)). Additionally, there was no difference in PDR between both arms in four studies^{12,13,25,26} (RR 1.06 [95% CI 0.91 – 1.24]).

APC was reported in all eight studies. There was no mean difference between CADe and non-CADe arms in terms of APC (0.93 vs 0.79; MD 0.14 [95% CI -0.04 – 0.32]; $I^2 = 89\%$, very low certainty evidence (see *Supplementary Table 3*)) and APPC (Eight studies, MD -0.11 [95% CI -0.52 – 0.30]). There was no mean difference between both arms for other outcomes: PPC^{9,11,12,26} (Four studies, MD 0.26 [95% CI -0.47 – 1.00]), and SSLPC^{11,13,25,27} (Four studies, MD 0.03 [95% CI -0.07 – 0.14]). There was high heterogeneity between studies for all these outcomes.

Harms

Inspection Time (Supplementary Figure 17)

Based on six studies^{9,11,13,25,26,28} - there was no difference between CADe and non-CADe arm in terms of mean inspection time (14.3 vs 13.4 minutes, MD 0.8 minutes [95% CI -0.18 – 1.90]; $I^2 = 73\%$; very low certainty evidence, (see *Supplementary Table 3*)).

Non-neoplastic lesion per colonoscopy (Supplementary Figure 18)

There was no difference between CADe and non-CADe arm for non-neoplastic lesions per colonoscopy^{9,11-13,25-28} (Eight studies, 0.52 vs 0.47; MD 0.14 [95% CI -0.07 – 0.34]; $I^2 = 99\%$; very low certainty evidence, (see *Supplementary Table 3*)).

Risk of Bias Assessment (Supplementary Figure 19)

This was assessed using the Cochrane bias assessment tool - ROBINS-I (Risk of Bias in Non-randomized Studies - of Interventions) as shown in *Supplementary Figure 3*. It showed an overall low risk of bias among included studies.

Sensitivity Analysis

- There was no benefit of CADe for ADR when studies were stratified according to indication for screening or surveillance colonoscopy only^{9,11,27,28} (RR 1.05 [95% CI 0.92 – 1.19]).
- In a leave-one-out analysis, after leaving out study by Levy et al., the difference in ADR between both arms was significant in favor of CADe (RR 1.16 [95% CI 1.01 – 1.33]; $I^2 = 74\%$) (*Supplementary Figure 2*).

Subgroup Analysis with Pooled ADR (Figure 2 and Supplementary Table 4)

- When studies were stratified according to the study design ADR was comparatively higher in CADe arm vs non-CADe arm in prospective studies^{11,25-27} (Four studies, RR 1.29 [95% CI 1.11 – 1.49]) whereas there was no difference in ADR in retrospective studies^{9,12,13,28} (Four studies, RR 0.97 [95% CI 0.86 – 1.09]).
- When only including studies that used GI Genius as the CADe system in the CADe arm, the ADR was lower than non-CADe arm^{9,12,28} (Three studies, RR 0.91 [95% CI 0.85 – 0.98], $I^2 = 21\%$). It is important to note that all three studies in the GI Genius cohort were retrospective in nature.
- All subgroups have a substantial number of studies (>3) and patients; hence the covariate distribution is of little significance for these subgroup analyses. The test for subgroup differences ($p < 0.05$) suggests that choice of study design and choice of CADe system significantly modifies the effect of intervention as seen in *Supplementary Table 4*.
- When studies were separated based on the type of control group - ADR was higher in the CADe assisted arm when using concurrent non-CADe control group (RR 1.26 [1.10 – 1.44], $I^2 = 41\%$)^{9,13,25,26}. The same was not true when studies used historical control group (RR 1.03 [0.87 – 1.21], $I^2 = 81\%$)^{9,11,12,27}. However, when comparing both subgroups for a difference in effect size, it did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.06$).

- Similarly, the ADR in CADe assisted arm was higher when studies were conducted at non-academic centers (RR 1.20 [1.07 – 1.35], $I^2=0\%$)^{11,13,27} whereas at academic centers there was no difference in ADR between both arms (RR 1.06 [0.89 – 1.26], $I^2=85\%$)^{9,12,25,26,28}. The subgroup differences did not reach statistical significance ($p=0.23$).
- There was no difference in ADR between both arms when studies were separated based on geographic location of the centers (east and west).

Meta-regression

Univariate meta-regression using baseline endoscopist ADR as a covariate influencing the effect size showed that a 1% increase in mean baseline ADR leads to reduction in effect size by 0.03% thereby meaning that with increase in ADR, we see decrease in effect size.

GRADE Quality Assessment (Supplementary Table 3)

The certainty of evidence from non-randomized trials starts at low. It can further be rated down to very low based on risk of bias, indirectness, imprecision, inconsistency (or heterogeneity), or publication bias. The quality of evidence can also be graded up if a large magnitude of effect exists, a dose-response gradient exists or if the consideration of effect of all plausible residual confounders increases our confidence in the estimated effect. We decided to rank the important outcomes (ADR, SSLDR, APC, Inspection time,>NNLPC) that were available from many studies to maximize the number of participants. All outcomes were graded with a very low certainty of evidence.

Discussion

The present systematic review and meta-analysis showed that CADe in colonoscopies neither improve the detection of colorectal neoplasia nor increases the burden of colonoscopy in real-world, non-randomized studies, questioning the generalizability of the results of randomized trials (**Figure 3**).

To our best knowledge, this study is the first meta-analysis to examine the use of CADe in a non-randomized setting with pooled data of nearly 10,000 patients. Previous meta-analyses of RCTs^{29,30} showed the benefits of CADe in improving ADR but RCTs have limitations in terms of their highly selective patient population with stringent inclusion and exclusion criteria and lack of autonomy for endoscopists and patients in terms of utilization of CADe and indications of

polypectomy. Overall, this runs the risk of ascertainment bias and lack of generalizability across varied clinical practice settings. Despite robust evidence in controlled settings, recent real-world studies have raised valid questions. It is important because a pragmatic and less controlled setting offers an opportunity to evaluate human-AI interaction without altering the physician or patient behavior and minimizing the Hawthorne effect or operator bias. Our study provides a contrasting perspective to those results previously known from the randomized studies.

The pooling of non-randomized trials was impacted by a high level of heterogeneity that was qualitatively and quantitatively distinct from the heterogeneity discovered in the prior meta-analysis of RCTs. In this analysis, one-third of the non-randomized studies favored the control arm for ADR, compared to none of the 21 RCTs in the previous meta-analysis¹. This qualitative difference generates a much higher degree of ambiguity as it does not apply only to the magnitude of the effect of CADe, but it puts in question the actual existence of any CADe-related benefit. An important point to make is that the analysis of Adenoma and Serrated lesion Per Colonoscopy supported the qualitative heterogeneity, favoring the control arm over the CADe arm, in the direction of the effect. Intriguingly, our study did not find any harm from CADe, whereas the previous meta-analysis found an increase in non-neoplastic lesion resection by 18% as well as in withdrawal time. The simultaneous lack of benefit and burden/harm is interesting, somewhat suggesting an under-utilization or a lack of effect of CADe.

The second reason of the clinical relevance of our study is the fact that an exploratory analysis showed a radical difference between non-randomized studies that adopted a prospective and a retrospective analysis. Half of the studies included in this analysis (4/8) demonstrated an improvement in ADR with CADe^{11,13,25,26}. Three of these studies were conducted prospectively^{11,25,26}. However, four other studies reported no difference in ADR^{9,12,27,28}, and three of these were retrospective studies^{9,12,28}. Prospective observational studies using a concurrent and not a historical cohort provide evidence that is closest to a pragmatic trial in a non-randomized context and with little heterogeneity. Retrospective studies, on the other hand, could introduce considerable selection bias. Our sensitivity analysis focusing on prospective studies was able to eliminate heterogeneity and provide the most reliable outcomes noting an improvement in overall ADR using CADe. However, considerable heterogeneity remained when only data from retrospective studies were examined. The test of subgroup differences revealed a statistically

significant subgroup effect ($p < 0.01$), indicating the importance of research design in CADe effect estimation. Furthermore, when excluding all studies that used a historical cohort group, ADR in the CADe arm was significantly higher than non-CADe arm and thereby reflecting a possible Hawthorne bias when a concurrent control group is used: **participating endoscopists may have been more aware to be involved in a formal CADe evaluation, potentially favouring the intervention. On the other hand, when using the historical control, this bias was minimized.** The study by Ladabaum et al., was used in both subgroups as it provided data for both a concurrent control group and a historical control group⁹. Thus, the methodology of effectiveness studies – i.e., retrospective versus prospective – may affect the overall estimate of CADe efficacy, indirectly mimicking the difference between non-randomized and randomized studies shown by our analysis. Additionally, when the intent of the procedure is screening or surveillance examination, CADe does not improve the ADR which could be secondary to a constant intent of adenoma detection equally in both the cohorts regardless of study design, and this could further emulate a near-controlled setting.

It could be argued that the hierarchical inferiority of non-randomized studies cannot put in doubt the outcomes shown by a meta-analysis of RCTs, especially when considering the over 20,000 patients enrolled in these RCTs. However, our analysis argues against the indiscriminate implementation of CADe, especially when considering its high cost. Effectiveness rather than efficacy measures the return for investment. Thus, careful monitoring of the effectiveness of such intervention, including a proper selection of an unbiased control, is needed. In this regard, a pragmatic randomized trial may be the optimal testing venue. In these pragmatic studies, new interventions are integrated into existing healthcare systems such as cancer screening programs, which makes study participants less biased to intervention³¹. Of note, the main difference between a randomized and non-randomized study on detection of colorectal neoplasia is not, as already stressed the risk of operator-bias, but a potential difference in the risk of selection bias that is higher in non-randomized than in randomized setting. In other words, we cannot exclude that unintentionally endoscopists allocate patients at higher risk of disease in the CADe than in the non-CADe arm in order to use CADe in those patients who may get more benefit. However, such selection bias would favour CADe rather than the opposite, further strengthening the results of our study. In addition, selection bias may be marginalized even in a non-randomized setting by

controlling for demographics and indications of colonoscopy that are the main determinants of prevalence of colorectal neoplasia.

The results of our study have important implications for clinical practice and contribute valuable data to the current understanding of this topic. Our strengths stem from our analysis that was conducted carefully, selecting studies that met specific criteria. We were able to categorize the studies based on the purpose of the colonoscopy, providing data for both - only screening and screening or surveillance. In neither category did the computer-aided detection (CADe) perform better than standard colonoscopy. We conducted additional analyses to address heterogeneity between the studies to understand how AI technology can best assist in colonoscopy and to identify what study design will optimally aid in achieving that goal. Our study provides important clinical insight into outcomes from complexities of human-AI interactions in this matter.

The limitations of our study include the use of heterogeneous observational cohort studies, which may have unmeasured and unobservable confounding and may not be effectively resolved by additional analysis and meta-analytic approaches. There is a paucity of data for certain outcomes (false positive rate, true histology rate) and subgroup analyses (stratification of outcomes based on bowel preparation and baseline ADR). All but one study included in this analysis did not clearly report the use of mucosal exposure devices and thus we could not account for the use of such devices which could improve ADR based on some recent studies^{13,32,33}. A few studies stratified data based on endoscopist baseline ADR and none of them found an association between ADR and endoscopist baseline ADR^{9,12,28}. Due to a heterogeneous definition of low and high detectors employed in these studies, this could not be aggregated. However, a meta-regression analysis in our study showed that with increase in baseline ADR, we see decrease in effect size/benefit of CADe assisted over non-assisted arm. Additionally, data for cost effectiveness is not available. In the future, studies should focus on the benefit of CADe for the individual endoscopist as it cannot be excluded that the interaction between endoscopists and CADe may affect the actual benefit of CADe intervention that may be lost when pooling all the endoscopists together. One study that was an outlier in our main analysis showed a slight imbalance in the detection of advanced adenomas between the two arms that could be at least partially explained by the fact that the enrollment time was during the COVID-19 pandemic period^{12,34}.

When considering the lack of ADR increase in studies based on historical controls, our data underline the need for a proactive monitoring on the outcomes of colonoscopy in order to compare the performances of individual endoscopists before and after CADe implementation. This may address possible barriers preventing CADe beneficial effect, such as endoscopists' reluctance to activate the CADe device or an inappropriate interaction between the endoscopist and the machine.

In summary, CADe in colonoscopy neither improves the detection of colorectal neoplasia nor increases burden of colonoscopy in the real-world, non-randomized studies. The contrasting nature of these findings compared to randomized studies implicates a greater role for real world data and raises a question if benefits and harms of CADe are not apparent due to a lack of a targeted study design. To address the uncertainties in the current literature, we recommend conducting additional randomized studies in a more pragmatic setting.

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Table 1. Study Characteristics

Study Name	Non-randomized Study Design	Indication	No. of Patients		Mean Age (y)		ADR (%)	
			AI	SC	AI	SC	AI	SC
Shaukat	-Prospective enrollment in AI arm -Historical Cohort for SC arm (preceding 6 months of same 3 endoscopists, baseline ADR 32.6%) -Ambulatory center, USA	Screen/Surveil	83	283	62.2	NA	54.2	40.6
Ishiyama	-Prospective enrollment in both arms -Propensity score matching (30 endoscopists - aware of being monitored) -University hospital, Japan	All	918	918	67	68	26.3	19.9
Shen	-Prospective enrollment in both arms -Alternating between CADe and SC every 2 weeks (same 1 endoscopist) -Academic Center, China	All	64	64	58.6	59	53.1	29.6
Quan	-Prospective enrollment in AI arm -Historical Cohort for SC arm (preceding 6 months of same 6 endoscopists, baseline ADR 37.8%) -2 community centers, USA	All**	256	249	62	63.5	53.1	47.7
Schauer	-Retrospective data collection (no screening colonoscopy) -AI arm preceded SC arm (13 endoscopists including 4 surgeons, baseline ADR 42%) -Ambulatory center, NZ	All	213	213	56	56	47.8	38.4
Levy	-Retrospective data collection -Historical Cohort for SC arm (preceding 6 months of same 30 endoscopists) -Academic medical center, Israel	All	1969	2175	63.8	63.4	30.3	35.2
Nehme	-Retrospective data collection (CADe activation at endoscopist discretion)	Screen/	403	641	62.4	63.1	50.3	53

	-Historical Control for SC arm (preceding 6 months of same 23 endoscopists, baseline ADR 49.3%) -Academic medical center, USA	Surveil						
Ladabaum	-Retrospective data collection -Concurrent and Historical Cohort for SC arm (Different endoscopists for concurrent control arm at different site, similar baseline ADR for endoscopist at both sites ~41%) -2 academic medical centers, USA	Screen/ Surveil	619	619	57.3	56.6	40	41.8 (HC) 35.8 (CC)

*ADR values in bold suggest a statistically significant difference.

** ADR and SSLDR data were based only on screening and surveillance patients.

AI – CADe, SC- Standard Colonoscopy or non-CADe

HC – Historical Control, CC – Concurrent Control

Figure Legend:

Figure 1: ADR (Adenoma Detection Rate): CADe assisted versus Standard Colonoscopy

Figure 2: Summary Plot for ADR and Subgroup Analysis

Figure 3: Benefits and Harms of CADe-assisted versus Standard Colonoscopy

*Main outcomes based on 6 or more studies

ADR = adenoma detection rate; SSLDR = sessile serrated lesion detection rate ; APC = mean adenoma per colonoscopy;>NNLPC = non-neoplastic lesion per colonoscopy

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